

Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices of Pregnant Women Regarding Iron Deficiency Anemia and Its Dietary Relationship: A Study in Al- Jazaeer Primary Health Care Center and Al-Diwaniyah Maternity and Children's Teaching Hospital in Al-Diwaniyah Governorate, Iraq

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Abstract

Background: Iron deficiency anemia (IDA) is a common global health concern, particularly during pregnancy, due to increased iron demands. It contributes to maternal and fetal complications, including low birth weight and preterm delivery. Despite antenatal care efforts, gaps in knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) toward IDA remain in Iraq. This study aimed to assess the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of pregnant women regarding IDA and its dietary implications in Al-Diwaniyah, Iraq. The goal was to identify misconceptions and behavioral gaps to guide future health education interventions.

Material and Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted among 400 pregnant women attending two antenatal clinics between January and July 2025. Data were collected using a structured, interviewer-administered questionnaire addressing socio-demographics, knowledge of IDA, attitudes toward supplementation, and dietary practices. **Results:** Of 400 women, 59.8% had been previously diagnosed with IDA. While 87.3% knew pregnancy is a risk factor, only 60% were aware of its complications. Regular iron tablet use was reported by 50.2%, with barriers including side effects, forgetfulness, and misconceptions. Despite 81.8% consuming mixed diets, 48.3% drank tea with meals, which impairs iron absorption. **Conclusions:** Although general awareness and positive attitudes were observed, substantial knowledge gaps and suboptimal practices persist. Targeted educational programs are recommended to address dietary misconceptions and improve iron supplement compliance during pregnancy.

Keywords: *Iron deficiency anemia, pregnancy nutrition, maternal health, dietary habits, iron supplements.*

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Introduction

Iron deficiency anemia (IDA) is the most widespread nutritional deficiency, resulting from inadequate iron reserves, and is diagnosed when hemoglobin levels fall below 11 g/dl or hematocrit drops below 33%, irrespective of the trimester (World Health Organization, 2024). It affects approximately 30% of the global population (World Health Organization, 2024). During pregnancy, physiological dilutional anemia commonly occurs because erythrocyte mass increases only by 15% to 25%, whereas plasma volume expands by 40% to 50% (American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists' Committee on Practice Bulletins—Obstetrics, 2021). Pregnancy-related IDA can result from several factors, including consuming tea or coffee immediately after meals, avoiding meat, following specific diets, shorter gestation periods, parasitic infections, or a history of heavy menstrual bleeding (Derman et al., 2021). Both the mother and fetus face significant risks from anemia, including higher rates of miscarriage, postpartum hemorrhage, fetal growth restriction, hypoxia, low birth weight, infections, early membrane rupture, and perinatal death. Additionally, pregnant women with IDA are at greater risk of thromboembolism, linked to reactive thrombocytosis (Duan et al., 2022). IDA manifests with a wide range of clinical symptoms. Reduced oxygen availability can lead to chest pain, rapid heart rate, palpitations, fatigue, and breathlessness. Inadequate oxygen supply to the gut may impair intestinal function, contributing to motility disorders, nutrient malabsorption, nausea, unintended weight loss, and discomfort. Reduced cerebral oxygenation can also trigger headaches, vertigo, mental fatigue, and difficulties with concentration, although these cognitive disturbances often improve after anemia is corrected (Roemhild et al., 2021). The National Academy of Sciences recommends pregnant women aim for 27 mg of elemental iron daily, and nursing mothers 9 mg (Stoffel et al., 2020). Iron deficiency anemia remains one of the most prevalent nutritional deficiencies among pregnant women worldwide,

posing significant risks to maternal and neonatal health. In low- and middle-income countries, the prevalence is considerably higher due to dietary insufficiencies, limited access to healthcare, and socio-economic challenges. Iraq, in particular, continues to report high rates of anemia among women of reproductive age. Within Al-Diwaniyah, recent studies have highlighted anemia as a persistent maternal health issue (Al-Mamoori & Al-Habib, n.d.; Al-Bashir & Jassim, 2024; Al-Obaidi & Al-Khafaji, 2024). Despite this, few studies have systematically assessed pregnant women's knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding this condition. Therefore, conducting this study in Al-Diwaniyah is justified to address this evidence gap and provide context-specific recommendations for maternal health improvement.

Methodology

A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted between January and July 2025 in Al-Jazaer Primary Health Care Center and Al-Diwaniyah Teaching Hospital for Obstetrics and Pediatrics, Al-Diwaniyah, Iraq, involving 400 pregnant women. Ethical approval was obtained from the institutional review board of the College of Medicine, University of Al-Qadisiyah. All participants were informed verbally about the study objectives and procedures and provided informed verbal consent prior to data collection. Inclusion criteria included all pregnant women of any gestational age who visited the mentioned health facilities and consented to participate. Exclusion criteria included non-pregnant women or those with other medical causes of anemia (e.g., thalassemia, bleeding disorders). A sample of 400 women was determined using Kish's formula, assuming a 63.3% prevalence of knowledge about IDA, 5% precision, and a 95% confidence level. A 15% buffer was added to account for non-response. A structured and validated Arabic questionnaire was administered face-to-face. It included five sections: socio-demographic data, medical and dietary history, knowledge about IDA, attitudes toward prevention and supplementation, and dietary/supplement practices. Data were

analyzed using SPSS version 25. Descriptive statistics (frequencies and percentages) summarized participants' characteristics. Associations between categorical variables were analyzed using Chi-square and Fisher's exact tests. Significance was set at $P \leq .05$. Exact P values are reported up to two decimal points; P values $< .001$ are reported as $P < .001$. No P value is reported as 0 or 1.

Results

The study involved 400 pregnant women with different educational backgrounds.

Figure 1. Pie Chart Showing the Distribution of Participants According to Their Educational Level

The most common level was college or university (26%), followed by those who were literate (22.3%), and secondary education (20.3%). Primary education was reported by 16% of participants, while 10.5% were illiterate, and only 5% had completed high school (figure 1).

Most participants were housewives (75.8%) and lived in cities (62.3%). Socioeconomically, 61.3% reported having enough income to some degree, while 25% had sufficient income, and 13.8% had insufficient income. Regarding pregnancy stages, 40% were in the first trimester, 31.8% in the second, and 28.2% in the third. Past pregnancy data showed that 27.8% had two previous pregnancies, 25.8% had three or more, 25.3% had one, and 21.3% were experiencing their first pregnancy. Regarding healthcare access, 64% of the participants reported using a car, while 36% accessed services on foot. Pregnancy spacing revealed that 44% had a gap of two years or more between pregnancies, 39% had less than two years, and 17% had no prior pregnancies. When asked about sources of pregnancy-related information, nearly half (49%) cited healthcare providers as their primary source, followed by other sources like family and friends (28.7%), the internet (12.5%), television (9.3%), and radio (0.5%) (Table 1).

Table 1. Demographic and Background Information

Category	Subcategory	Counts	% of Total	Cumulative %
Educational level	Tertiary /university or higher	104	26.0%	26.0%
	Read and write	89	22.3%	48.3%
	Illiterate	42	10.5%	58.8%
	Secondary	81	20.3%	79.0%
	Primary	64	16.0%	95.0%
	Higher school	20	5.0%	100.0%
Occupation	Worker	97	24.3%	24.3%
	Housewife	303	75.8%	100.0%
Place of residence	Urban	249	62.3%	62.3%
	Rural	151	37.8%	100.0%
Socioeconomic Status	Enough	100	25.0%	25.0%
	Enough to some extent	245	61.3%	86.3%
	Not Enough	55	13.8%	100.0%
Pregnancy Trimester	Week 1 to 12	160	40.0%	40.0%
Previous Pregnancies	0	85	21.3%	21.3%
	2	111	27.8%	49.0%
	≥ 3	103	25.8%	74.8%
	1	101	25.3%	100.0%
Primary Healthcare Access	Walking	144	36.0%	36.0%

	By car	256	64.0%	100.0%
Pregnancy Span	None	68	17.0%	17.0%
	≥ 2 years	176	44.0%	61.0%
	Less than 2 years	156	39.0%	100.0%
	Others	115	28.7%	28.7%
Information Source	Healthcare provider	196	49.0%	77.8%
	Radio	2	0.5%	78.3%
	Internet	50	12.5%	90.8%
	Television	37	9.3%	100.0%

Among the 400 participants, 59.8% reported having been diagnosed with IDA, while 40.3% had no prior diagnosis (figure 2). In terms of dietary habits, most participants (81.8%) consumed a mixed diet that included both plant

and animal sources. A smaller proportion (13.8%) reported following a mainly plant-based diet, while only 4.5% primarily consumed animal-based foods (Table 2).

Table 2. Medical and Dietary History

Category	Subcategory	Counts	% of Total	Cumulative %
Diagnosed with IDA	No	161	40.3%	40.3%
	Yes	239	59.8%	100.0%
Usual Diet	Mixed Plant & Animal	327	81.8%	81.8%
	Mainly Plant-based	55	13.8%	95.5%
	Mainly Animal-based	18	4.5%	100.0%

A significant proportion of participants (80.3%) reported having heard of IDA, indicating a generally high level of awareness. Additionally, 87.3% recognized that pregnant women are at greater risk of developing IDA. However, only 59.5% correctly disagreed with the misconception that IDA does not cause maternal complications during pregnancy, while 40.5% believed otherwise. Regarding fetal health, 60.5% of women correctly denied that iron deficiency has no effect on the baby's development or outcomes such as premature birth or low birth weight, whereas 39.5% held inaccurate beliefs. Awareness of symptoms was

relatively high, with 85.8% identifying fatigue and weakness as signs of IDA, and 84.3% recognizing that dizziness or fainting could be associated with low iron levels. Most respondents recognized the preventive role of a diet, with 79.3% stating that consuming iron-rich foods helps avert anemia. Familiarity with animal sources was likewise high, 81.0 % correctly identified meat, liver, and poultry as good iron sources. In contrast, misconceptions about plant sources were common: 41.5% erroneously believed that spinach, lentils, green peppers, and beans do not contain iron, while only 58.5% rejected this misconception (as in table 3).

Table 3. Women's Attitudes Regarding IDA, Iron Supplements and Diet

Category	Subcategory	Counts	% of Total	Cumulative %
Regular antenatal checkup of blood tests are essential during pregnancy.	Strongly Agree	189	47.3%	47.3%
	Agree	152	38.0%	85.3%
	Neutral	27	6.8%	92.0%
	Disagree	32	8.0%	100.0%
IDA considered to be dangerous during pregnancy.	Agree	238	59.5%	59.5%
	Disagree	14	3.5%	63.0%
	Neutral	37	9.3%	72.3%
	Strongly Agree	111	27.8%	100.0%
It's essential to take special diet during pregnancy.	Strongly Agree	163	40.8%	
	Agree	162	40.5%	81.3%

	Neutral	43	10.8%	92.0%
	Disagree	32	8.0%	100.0%
Drinking of tea with meal cannot effect on our health.	Strongly Agree	16	4.0%	4.0%
	Agree	64	16.0%	20.0%
	Disagree	204	51.0%	71.0%
	Neutral	53	13.3%	84.3%
	Strongly Disagree	63	15.8%	100.0%
Iron-rich diet alone is enough to prevent anemia during pregnancy.	Strongly Agree	74	18.5%	18.5%
	Agree	180	45.0%	63.5%
	Disagree	105	26.3%	89.8%
	Neutral	37	9.3%	99.0%
	Strongly Disagree	4	1.0%	100.0%

Understanding of nutrient interactions was mixed. Fewer than half (47.3 %) knew that vitamin C-rich foods enhance iron absorption, and 52.8 % were unaware of this effect. Moreover, 63.0 % incorrectly believed that drinking tea, coffee, or soft drinks with meals increases iron absorption, highlighting a substantial gap in knowledge about dietary inhibitors of iron uptake. Most women showed a positive attitude toward routine antenatal care, with 47.3% strongly agreeing and 38.0% agreeing that regular blood tests during pregnancy are essential. The majority also

viewed IDA as dangerous during pregnancy, as indicated by 59.5% agreeing and 27.8% strongly agreeing with this statement. A large proportion of participants recognized the importance of dietary measures, with 81.3% agreeing or strongly agreeing that a special diet is necessary during pregnancy. However, misconceptions remain about the effect of tea consumption on iron absorption, with 20.0% agreeing or strongly agreeing that tea with meals does not affect health, while over half (51.0%) disagreed, and 15.8% strongly disagreed (as in table 4).

Table 4. Association between Socio-Demographic Factors and Knowledge about IDA and Its Complications

Is occupation associated with knowledge that pregnant women are at higher risk of IDA?			
Factor (Subcategory)	Knowledge - YES	Knowledge - NO	P-value
Worker	97	0	< 0.001
Housewife	252	51	
Is place of residence associated with knowing that IDA causes maternal or fetal complications?			
Factor (Subcategory)	Knowledge - NO	Knowledge - YES	< 0.001
Urban	127	122	
Rural	115	36	
Is socioeconomic status associated with knowing that IDA causes maternal or fetal complications?			
Factor (Subcategory)	Knowledge - YES	Knowledge - NO	0.136
Enough	76	24	
Enough to some extent	192	53	
Not Enough	49	6	
Is education level associated with knowing tea reduces iron absorption?			
Factor (Subcategory)	Knowledge - YES	Knowledge - NO	< 0.001
Tertiary/university, higher	58	46	
R&W	42	47	
Illiterate	34	8	
Secondary	61	20	
Primary	42	22	
Higher school	15	5	

The majority of participants (67.5%) reported visiting primary health centers regularly during

their current pregnancy. However, 56.5% indicated that they continued with their usual

diet rather than adopting special dietary practices after becoming pregnant. Encouragingly, 66.0% reported consuming vitamin C-rich juices such as lemon or orange with meals, which can aid iron absorption. On the other hand, 48.3% admitted to drinking tea with meals, a habit known to inhibit iron absorption. Dietary intake of iron-rich foods was relatively strong, with 82.3% consuming meat, fish, eggs, and green leafy vegetables frequently. Occupation was significantly associated with knowledge that pregnant women are at higher risk of IDA ($p < 0.001$). All working women ($n = 97$) correctly identified this risk, while many housewives (51 of 303) lacked awareness. Place of residence also significantly influenced knowledge of IDA complications ($p < 0.001$) (as in figure 2).

Figure 2. Pie Chart Illustrating the Proportion of Participants Diagnosed with Iron Deficiency Anemia

Only 36 rural residents were aware of maternal or fetal risks, compared to 122 urban residents, indicating a knowledge gap by location. Socioeconomic status was not significantly linked to knowledge of IDA complications ($p = 0.136$), despite awareness differences among economic groups. Education level was significantly linked to knowledge about tea's inhibitory effect on iron absorption ($p < 0.001$). Those with secondary and higher education, especially tertiary/university, had better awareness (58 aware vs. 46 unaware) than those who could only read/write or were illiterate (Table 4). Beliefs about tea's health effects also

significantly influenced behavior ($p < 0.001$); those who disagreed that “tea doesn't affect health” avoided tea with meals—115 in “disagree” and 39 in “strongly disagree” groups did not drink tea with meals, compared to 6 and 16 in “strongly agree” and “agree” groups.

Discussion

This study assessed the knowledge, attitudes, and practice (KAP) among expectant women in Al-Diwaniyah, Iraq, regarding iron deficiency anemia (IDA) and its nutritional associations. Results showed moderate levels in each realm, with average scores for knowledge, attitude, and practice being 65.79, 69.06, and 55.03, respectively. Such results pinpoint important gaps between awareness and actual health practice, with consequent implications for the application of specific, targeted measures in public health in order to optimize maternal health outcomes. The demographic profile of the 400 pregnant participants shows a relatively diverse population in terms of education, socioeconomic background, and reproductive history. The most commonly reported educational level was tertiary or university, indicating a moderately educated sample. However, a significant portion had only basic literacy or secondary education, and 10.5% were illiterate. This aligns with other studies: In Al-Amara survey, it was found that only 50.3% had only basic education, in Baghdad only 28.7% had basic education and only 14% had advanced secondary school education (Alabedi et al., 2020; Saeed, 2024). Education plays a vital role in health literacy and decision-making during pregnancy, and similar disparities in education have been linked to gaps in knowledge and practices related to IDA. Most women were housewives (75.8%), a trend also seen in Al-Amara (56.8%) and Baghdad (87%), underscoring women's scant participation in the workforce and the impact on autonomy and health-seeking practice (Alabedi et al., 2020; Saeed, 2024) a finding consistent with other regional studies, where non-working status is common among pregnant women and often linked to reduced health autonomy and limited access to information (Kaya et al., 2023). Urban residence was more prevalent (62.3%), and this

urban-rural divide has been shown to affect access to health services and educational resources, with rural women generally having less exposure to health promotion efforts. Socioeconomic data revealed that 61.3% of participants had income “enough to some extent,” indicating moderate financial stability, while 13.8% reported insufficient income. Economic status is a key determinant of dietary quality and access to supplements, and previous studies have consistently found it to be significantly associated with anemia prevalence (Khan et al., 2020). Pregnancy distribution was fairly balanced across all trimesters, with a slightly higher percentage (40%) in the first trimester. Almost half of the women had either one or two previous pregnancies, and 44% experienced interpregnancy intervals of two years or longer. In terms of healthcare access, most participants used a car, which may indicate relatively good physical access to services. However, reliance on walking could still create a barrier for some. Lastly, information sources were mainly healthcare providers (49%), with others relying on informal sources like family and friends, media, or the internet. The prominence of healthcare professionals as the main source is encouraging, as it suggests opportunities to reinforce accurate health education, especially regarding IDA and supplement use. In Al-Amara, health centers were the main source (56.6%). This reinforces a leading role for health professionals in delivering correct, implementable health education, particularly on IDA prevention and supplement intake (Alabedi et al., 2020). The findings indicate that 59.8% of participants reported IDA, a rate consistent with global data demonstrating that approximately 40–50% of pregnancies in low- and middle-income countries are affected, with iron deficiency being the primary cause (de Paula Ayres-Silva, 2023). This finding is consistent with national statistics in Iraq, with Al-Amara recording a higher prevalence, consistent with national statistics from the Nutrition Research Institute recording 38% among expectant women (Alabedi et al., 2020). In the Baghdad Teaching Hospital survey, the same problem emerged, where nearly two-thirds of participants had iron supplementation

requirements and demonstrated dietary practice gaps despite awareness (Saeed, 2024). Nutrient analysis reveals that although 81.8% consumed mixed diets comprising both plant and animal sources, this does not necessarily guarantee adequate iron absorption, given that heme iron from animal products exhibits high bioavailability (14–30%) compared to non-heme iron (5–12%) found in plant-based foods (Moustarah & Daley, 2023). The subgroup predominantly consuming plant-based diets (13.8%) may be at an increased risk, as numerous reviews associate vegetarian or vegan diets with reduced iron stores and an elevated risk of anemia (López-Moreno et al., 2025). This risk profile also echoes the findings in the Baghdad study, where, despite the perceived knowledge about green leafy vegetables and meat being a good source of iron, practice in reality remained suboptimal, with tea consumption during meals still prevalent in 36.3% of participants. Nonetheless, adaptive mechanisms, such as enhanced non-heme iron absorption in certain individuals, can offer partial compensation (López-Moreno et al., 2025). The results indicate that there is fundamental awareness about IDA and its symptoms, particularly in relation to maternal and fetal health. Approximately 40.5% of respondents believed that IDA does not result in maternal complications, and 39.5% were unaware of its potential effects on the fetus. At Al-Amara survey demonstrated limited awareness about IDA consequences, and the Baghdad survey concluded that nearly 30% were oblivious about risks in the fetus. This consistent pattern in research underscores enhanced antenatal education concerning severe health outcomes for iron deficiency anemia (Alabedi et al., 2020; Saeed, 2024). Knowledge about diet and iron intake followed a similar pattern, the findings are in line with studies conducted both within Iraq and in neighboring countries (Al-Khazraji et al., 2022), in their study in Baghdad, found good IDA knowledge in 76.5% of pregnant women, although poor awareness on dietary enhancers and inhibitors. In a study in Jordan (Al-Qudah et al., 2021) found good overall awareness but poor nutritional literacy on iron absorption. Regarding dietary habits, a majority of participants agreed that maintaining

a special diet during pregnancy is essential, indicating awareness of the role of nutrition in maternal health. However, misconceptions about dietary practices still exist. One in five participants (20%) either agreed or strongly agreed that drinking tea with meals does not affect their health, despite evidence that tea inhibits non-heme iron absorption due to its polyphenol content. This highlights the need for more detailed dietary education during pregnancy. The results reveal significant patterns in pregnant women's practices related to IDA and diet. The regular visits to primary health centers during pregnancy, suggesting a high level of engagement with maternal healthcare services. Despite this, 56.5% of women did not adopt specialized dietary changes during pregnancy and continued with their usual diets, which could limit efforts to prevent IDA. This aligns with findings by (Zulfiqar et al., 2021) who reported that low iron intake and poor dietary habits were significant contributors to the high prevalence of anemia among pregnant women in Pakistan. Encouragingly, most of women consumed vitamin C-rich juices, such as lemon or orange, with meals, which enhances the absorption of non-heme iron. However, 48.3% of participants also reported drinking tea with meals, which inhibits iron absorption due to its tannin content. This duality of practices reflects a common issue highlighted in (Benson et al., 2021) who noted that despite improved dietary iron intake, habits like tea consumption and antacid use can significantly impair iron bioavailability. The findings highlight key socio-demographic factors affecting knowledge of IDA and its complications during pregnancy. Occupation influenced awareness, with employed women recognizing pregnancy as high-risk for IDA, while housewives had lower awareness. Urban women had significantly greater knowledge than rural women, indicating disparities in health education access (Alzaheb, 2020) found higher urban awareness and lower anemia prevalence. Socioeconomic status did not significantly affect awareness, but education level was strongly linked to knowledge about dietary inhibitors like tea. Women with higher education understood these better, with less-

educated women showing the largest knowledge gaps (Alzaheb, 2020; Mostafa et al., 2022).

Conclusion

This study provides a comprehensive assessment of iron deficiency anemia (IDA) knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) among pregnant women, with several significant associations with socio-demographic, medical, and behaviorally connected factors. Although rudimentary IDA awareness prevailed among the greater part, key gaps prevailed in identifying complications and dietetic sources. Misinformation, particularly in vegetable-based iron and tea consumption, persists in spite of positive overall attitudes towards prevention. Practice demonstrated a lack of concordance between awareness and practice, where suboptimum dietary modification, non-uniform compliance with supplements, and incorrect intake timing negate anemia prevention. Socioeconomic status, parity, and pregnancy trimester were significant predictors of IDA prevalence, while education level and occupation were stronger predictors of influencing knowledge. Fighting these determinants with culturally appropriate, evidence-based interventions is the key for improving maternal and fetal health outcomes in low-resource settings.

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